

DESIGN OF COMPOSITE PROPELLER BLADE OF TURBOPROP AIRCRAFT CONSIDERING ON SELF HEALING

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Keywords: Propeller Blade, Turboprop, Design, Test

ABSTRACT

In this study, aerodynamic and structural design of the composite propeller blade for a regional turboprop aircraft is performed. The thin and wide chord propeller blade of high speed turboprop aircraft should have proper strength and stiffness to carry various kinds of loads such as high aerodynamic bending and twisting moments and centrifugal forces. Therefore the skin-spar-foam sandwich structure using high strength and stiffness carbon/epoxy composite materials is used to improve the lightness. A specific design procedure is proposed in this work as follows; firstly the aerodynamic configuration design, which is acceptable for the design requirements, is carried out using the in-house code developed by authors, secondly the structure design loads are determined through the aerodynamic load case analysis, thirdly the spar flange and the skin are preliminarily sized by consideration of major bending moments and shear forces using both the netting rule and the rule of mixture, and finally, the stress analysis is performed to confirm the structural safety and stability using finite element analysis commercial code, MSC. NASTRAN/PATRAN. Furthermore the additional analysis is performed to confirm the structural safety due to bird strike impact on the blade during flight operation using a commercial code, ANSYS. Finally, the self-healing concept for developed propeller was studied.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, the need for developing the environmental and eco-friendly aircrafts with increased fuel efficiency is being emphasized as an eco-friendly requirement in response to high oil prices. In this study, structural design and analysis of the propeller blade for turboprop aircraft, which will be a high speed transportation system for the next generation, was performed. In order to investigate the structural safety and stability, stress analysis was performed by finite element analysis code MSC. NASTRAN. Finally, it is investigated that designed blade have high efficiency and structural safety to analyze of aerodynamic and structural design results.

Many studies for advanced turboprop were performed. Among the previous studies, Roy H. Lange performed research about a review of advanced turboprop transport aircraft in 1986[1]. F. Farassat et al. performed the study on advanced turboprop noise prediction based on recent theoretical results in 1987[2]. This paper deals with the development of a high speed propeller noise prediction code at Langley Research Center. J. A. Liser et al. studied aeroacoustic design of a 6-bladed propeller in 1997[3].

In this work, aerodynamic and structural design of the propeller blade for an advanced turboprop aircraft, which will be used for a next generation regional commercial aircraft in Korea, are carried out. In the aerodynamic design, the parametric studies are performed to decide an optimum aerodynamic configuration having a specific HS1 series airfoil. In structural design, the proposed propeller blade uses the carbon/epoxy composite skin and spar and urethane foam core sandwich type structure, so-called skin-spar-foam sandwich, is adopted. To finalize the proposed propeller structure design, the prototype propeller is manufactured, tested and compared with the structural analysis results.

2 AERODYNAMIC DESIGN

There are several design methods to size the aerodynamic blade configuration parameters such as chord length and twist angle. This work uses both the vortex theory and the blade element theory for

this purpose. The propeller blade airfoil configuration is an important factor to determine various performance parameters. In this work, the HS1 series airfoil is selected for the design purpose. The number of blades is selected as 8 blades based on previous studies[4]. Figure 1 shows aerodynamic designed blade. Table 1 shows blade angle and chord length distribution at each blade section. Table 2 shows aerodynamic performance calculation results

Figure 1: Aerodynamic configuration of the proposed propeller blade.

Section	r/R	β [degree]	Cr[mm]
A	0.20	65	347
B	0.30	63	347
C	0.40	59	348
D	0.50	55	352
E	0.60	50	348
F	0.70	46	338
G	0.80	41	318
H	0.90	39	248
I	1.00	35	53

Table 1: Blade angle and chord length distribution at each blade section.

Item	results
J	2.12
Efficiency [%]	87.8
Thrust [N]	11563
Power [HP]	2499
β at 75% [degree]	43.9

Table 2: Aerodynamic performance calculation results.

3 STRUCTURAL DESIGN

Structural loads applied to the propeller blade are divided into major aerodynamic loads and subsidiary loads due to dynamic and centrifugal forces in rotation, ice, temperature and humidity effects, faults of the system, etc. in service. It is very difficult to analysis all these loads because they are related to each other. However, because aerodynamic loads are much higher than others, they are mainly considered to avoid the design complication in preliminary structural design. Figure 2 shows schematic blade sectional view with the skin-spar-foam sandwich. Figure 3 shows bending moment diagram at design load cases

Preliminary structural design is initially carried out using the netting rule method. According to the netting rule, the principal load directional thickness of main spar flange can be sized by the cripple buckling strength. After initial sizing, the structure is modified using the rule of mixture that can consider approximately 10% additional load in off-loading directions at other inclined fiber directional plies. Therefore the initially sized 0° ply flange thickness by the netting rule is added by ±45° and 90° plies. In order to reduce the weight as well as to strengthen both the dynamic stability and the buckling strength, the sandwich structure with the urethane foam core is applied. The main spar flange is extended to the blade tip, and its thickness is gradually decreased along the blade radius to reduce the weight.

Figure 2: Schematic blade sectional view with the skin -spar-foam sandwich.

Figure 3: Bending moment diagram at design load cases

The structural analysis is performed using a commercial code MSC. NASTAN and the post processing program MSC. PATRAN. The element type used for the analysis is the PCOMP 4-node shell element[5]. Tsai-Wu failure criterion is used to find the structural safety. According to stress analysis results, it is found that maximum compressive stress and tensile stress on the skin are 84MPa and 90MPa, and compressive stress and tensile stress at the spar are 74MPa and 69MPa. Figure 4 shows the spanwise stress distribution of the outer skin (1st ply).

The buckling analysis also is done by the finite element method. The buckling analysis finite element model is the same as the static analysis model. The buckling load factor means the ratio of the buckling load to the applied load. The minimum buckling load factor is found as 4.8 that are confirmed as safe from buckling. Figure 5 shows first buckling mode shape.

Figure 4: Spanwise stress distribution of skin (1st ply).

Figure 5: First buckling mode shape.

4 IMPACT DAMAGE ANALYSIS

The fluid–structure interaction analysis has been used as a coupled analysis method for the bird strike impact analysis. The coupled analysis means that consideration of the effect by interaction in case fields are combined. In this study, the bird strike phenomenon is analyzed using a commercial code, ANSYS. Generally, there are various kinds of birds in nature. However, chickens are mostly used for the bird strike test instead of wild birds because of easy acquisition. In this work, a chicken size bird is selected as a bird strike analysis model. Figure 6 shows a simulated bird model for the

analysis, and its mechanical properties are shown in Table 3. The hydrodynamic material is applied to the bird modeling. Figure 6 shows the finite element modeling of bird and blade using triangular shell elements. The location of impact region is assumed as 75% of blade spanwise. According to the impact analysis results, it is found that maximum spanwise stress and deformation on impact region of the skin are 182.65MPa and 33.6mm respectively, and the maximum deflection at the blade tip is 78.0mm.

Item	Value
Density(Kg/m ³)	950
Bulk modulus (pa)	2.2e9
Diameter (m)	0.114
Length (m)	0.228
Mass (Kg)	1.8144
Initial velocity (m/s)	197

Table 3: Mechanical properties of simulated bird.

Figure 6: Bird strike modeling using finite element meshes.

5 INVESTIGATION ON SELF-HEALING OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

The cracks in the blade structure are a critical problem in composite materials during their service in structural applications. The development of cracks brings about serious failure of the structures and then reduces their lifetimes. Therefore, early diagnosis of damage becomes necessary for removing the catastrophic failure. Recently, self-healing composite structures have attracted increasing research interests. This study was performed investigation on self-healing of composite structure. Figure 7 shows the concept of self-healing epoxy based composite with epoxy loaded microcapsules. The self-healing concept using embedded microcapsules is shown in Fig. 7. A microencapsulated liquid monomer healing agent is embedded in a structural polymer matrix containing a catalyst capable of polymerizing the healing agent. When the material is damaged cracks occur, rupturing the microcapsules and releasing the healing agent into the crack plane through capillary action. The healing agent contacts the catalyst, triggering polymerization that bonds the crack faces closed[6, 7]. The target composite blade structure will be applied with the self-healing concept.

Figure 7: The concept of self-healing epoxy based composite with epoxy loaded microcapsules.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, both aerodynamic and structural design of the propeller blade for an advanced regional turboprop aircraft is performed.

An optimum aerodynamic configuration of the propeller blade is proposed through the parametric studies. The propeller blade airfoil is an important factor to determine a good propeller performance. In this work the HS1 series airfoil is selected for the design purpose based on existing application examples. The proposed propeller shows better aerodynamic performance than other similar class existing propellers.

In structural design, the carbon/epoxy fabric skin-spar and urethane foam core sandwich composite structure is used to endure effectively various loads. In order to evaluate the designed structure, structural analysis is performed using the finite element method. It is found that the designed blade has a good structural integrity. Finally, study on self-healing concept of blade structure was performed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by Basic Science Research Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by the Ministry of Education (No. 2018R1D1A1B07043553).

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